

Cosolvent effects on the complexation of the antifungal propiconazole nitrate with β -cyclodextrin: A combined molecular dynamics and NMR study

Dragos L. Isac^{a,†}, Petru Tîrnovan^{a,†}, Alina Nicolescu^a, Adrian Fifere^a, Andrei Neamtu^{a,b,c,*} , Mariana Pinteala^a

^a Center of Advanced Research in Bionanocojugates and Biopolymers, "Petru Poni" Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry Iasi, Grigore Ghica Voda Al. No. 41A, Iasi 700487, Romania

^b Department of Physiology, "Grigore T. Popa" University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Universitatii Str. No. 16, Iasi 700115, Romania

^c TRANSCEND Centre, Regional Institute of Oncology (IRO) Iasi, Str. General Henri Mathias Berthelot Nr. 2-4, 700483 Iasi, Romania

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the effects of cosolvents in cyclodextrin (CyD)-drug complexation is essential for optimizing drug formulations, as cosolvents influence solubility, stability, and binding affinity. In this study, the inclusion complexation of propiconazole nitrate (PCZH-NO₃) with β -cyclodextrin (β -CyD) in mixed dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)/water solvent systems was investigated using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. MD simulations revealed that DMSO exhibits a strong affinity for the β -CyD cavity, effectively displacing water molecules even at low concentrations highlighting the competitive nature of DMSO and PCZH-NO₃ for inclusion within the β -CyD cavity. Enhanced sampling simulation techniques and potential of mean force (PMF) calculations demonstrated that complexation is most favorable at low DMSO concentrations (~5 % v/v), with a gradual decrease in binding affinity as DMSO levels increase, ultimately leading to complex destabilization at high DMSO ratios. ¹H-NMR and ROESY spectra confirmed these findings, with chemical shift variations and ROESY cross-peaks indicating a weakening of host-guest interactions with increasing DMSO concentration. The results provide molecular-level insights into the role of cosolvents in modulating drug-CyD interactions, highlighting the need to tailor solvent environments to enhance the stability and efficacy of β -CyD inclusion complexes for pharmaceutical applications.

1. Introduction

Fungal infections can range from mild skin conditions to life-threatening systemic infections, and their incidence has increased in recent years due to factors such as population growth, aging, and immune suppression (Almeida et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2023; Santoro et al., 2021; Thiyahuddin et al., 2019). Additionally, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated the situation. Individuals affected by COVID-19, especially the elderly and those with compromised immune systems, are highly vulnerable to opportunistic fungal

pathogens (Chavda et al., 2023). In this context, anti-fungal drugs play a crucial role in the prevention and treatment of these infections, but their efficacy and safety depend on various factors such as the type and severity of the infection, the host immune response, and the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the drugs. Some of the major classes of anti-fungal drugs include polyenes (Carolus et al., 2020; Zotchev, 2003), azoles (Assress et al., 2021), echinocandins (Szymański et al., 2022), allylamines (El-Sayed et al., 2020), and pyrimidine analogs (Jeelan Basha and Goudgaon, 2021), each with specific mechanisms of action and spectra of activity. In addition, higher toxicity on humans,

Abbreviations: CyD, Cyclodextrin; β -CyD, B-cyclodextrin; PCZ, Propiconazole; PCZH-NO₃, Propiconazole Nitrate; DMSO, Dimethyl Sulfoxide; MD, Molecular Dynamics; NMR, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance; PMF, Potential of Mean Force; US, Umbrella Sampling; ROESY, Rotating Frame Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy; QSAR, Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship; RMSF, Root Mean Square Fluctuations; RMSD, Root Mean Square Displacement; RDF, Radial Distribution Function; GAFF, General Amber Force Field; RESP, Restrained Electrostatic Potential; COM, Center of Mass.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: andrei.neamtu@umfiiasi.ro (A. Neamtu).

† Co-first authors with equal contributions.

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lower bioavailability and water solubility, the development of drug resistance, drug interactions, and adverse effects (Benitez and Carver, 2019; Li et al., 2021; Sanglard, 2019; Wiederhold, 2017) can limit the clinical utility of these drugs, highlighting the need for ongoing research and development of new anti-fungal agents or new formulations for the existing ones (Waghule et al., 2020).

Triazoles are a class of substances that have found important medical applications due to their antifungal properties. These compounds are effective against a broad spectrum of fungal infections, including candidiasis (Andes et al., 2004; Fakhim et al., 2017), aspergillosis (Jović et al., 2019; Pfaller et al., 2011), and cryptococcosis (Miller et al., 2004; Pfaller et al., 2011). Triazoles have been shown to be safe and effective for the treatment of these infections, with few adverse effects reported. Studies have also demonstrated their superiority over older antifungal agents, such as amphotericin B (Zhou et al., 2022), in terms of both efficacy and safety, which makes them a valuable treatment option for individuals with compromised immune systems, such as those with HIV/AIDS, cancer, or undergoing organ transplantation (Cronin and Chandrasekar, 2010; Gomes et al., 2014; Nivoix et al., 2009). Triazoles inhibit the production of ergosterol, a key component of the fungal cell membrane. Ergosterol is essential for the structural integrity and function of the fungal membrane, and its inhibition leads to increased membrane permeability and impaired cellular function. In addition, triazoles may also interfere with other cellular processes, such as DNA synthesis and cell division, which can further contribute to their antifungal activity (Nehra et al., 2021). Examples of triazoles used in clinical practice include voriconazole (Theuretzbacher et al., 2006), itraconazole (De Beule and Van Gestel, 2001), and posaconazole (Li et al., 2010).

Propiconazole (1-(2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-propyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-

ylmethyl)-1H-1,2,4-triazole, [PCZ]) is a widely used antifungal agent that belongs to the triazole family of compounds. It is often used in agrochemicals due to its superior antifungal activity when compared to other commercial azole compounds, but it is not commonly used in clinical settings due to concerns about increased toxicity. Some reports have suggested that exposure to propiconazole may be associated with certain health risks, such as liver damage (Hester et al., 2012), reproductive and developmental toxicity (Costa et al., 2015; Vieira et al., 2017), and neurotoxicity (Sanchez et al., 2020). However, these effects have mostly been observed in animal models or *in vitro* studies, and the clinical relevance of these findings is not yet clear.

In our previous studies (Fifere et al., 2012; Marangoci et al., 2011; Minea et al., 2016), we found that propiconazole nitrate (PCZH—NO₃) (Fig. 1), a derivative of propiconazole, had good antifungal activity and lower toxicity compared to the unmodified PCZ form. However, PCZH—NO₃ is hydrophobic, which limits its bioavailability. To address this issue, we formulated PCZH—NO₃ as an inclusion complex with both substituted and unsubstituted β -cyclodextrins (β -CyD) (Fig. 1). Cyclodextrins (CyDs) and their derivatives have been extensively used in the past for the formation of host-guest complexes (Balan-Porcărașu et al., 2023; Corciova et al., 2015; Farcas et al., 2008; Harabagi et al., 2004; Sarkar et al., 2022; Silion et al., 2019; Spulber et al., 2008; Varganici et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2021).

This paved the way for a wide range of biomedical applications (Adam et al., 2002; Agnes et al., 2022; Craciun et al., 2023; Mavridis and Yannakopoulou, 2020; Sardaru et al., 2021), especially in constructing more effective supramolecular architectures to be used as drug delivery systems (Ardeleanu et al., 2018; Celebioglu and Uyar, 2020; Marangoci et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2021). Our *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies confirmed

Fig. 1. The chemical structure of propiconazole nitrate (PCZH—NO₃), with atom numbering nomenclature used in this study shown in the upper-right. Below, β -cyclodextrin is depicted in both three-dimensional (3D) and planar projections, illustrating the conventional atom position nomenclature within the glycosidic units.

that PCZH—NO₃/β-CyD complexes exhibit improved water solubility, resulting in increased antifungal activity at lower concentrations and reduced toxicity. However, due to the hydrophobic nature of PCZH—NO₃, cosolvents must be used in the complexation process. The use of cosolvents is a common practice in the formation of drug-cyclodextrin inclusion complexes because they can improve the solubility and stability of the drug and the cyclodextrin in the same solvent system and promote the formation of the complex. In addition, cosolvents can reduce the crystallization tendency of the drug, resulting in a higher yield of the complex. The type and concentration of the cosolvent can influence the complexation efficiency and properties of the complex. Polar cosolvents such as ethanol, methanol, and DMSO have been shown to enhance the complexation of hydrophobic drugs with cyclodextrins by promoting the solubility of the drug and the cyclodextrin in the aqueous medium (Saokham et al., 2018). For hydrophobic drugs, nonpolar cosolvents such as chloroform can also be used to dissolve the drug and cyclodextrin in the same solvent system. However, these should be used with caution as they can also interfere with the formation of the complex.

Various theoretical approaches have been used to study cyclodextrins and their complexes with various compounds, such as *ab-initio* (Oqmhula et al., 2020), DFT (Kumar et al., 2023, 2024b) and semi-empirical quantum calculations (Fifere et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2020), molecular docking (Cheriet et al., 2022), quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSARs) (Jeschke and Cole, 2019), machine learning (Ma et al., 2022), Monte Carlo (Choi et al., 2000) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations (Mazurek et al., 2021). These well-established techniques in materials science, chemistry, biochemistry, molecular physiology, and pharmaceutical sciences have proven to be a powerful tool for studying cyclodextrin drug complexes. In particular, MD simulations represent a very attractive approach for several reasons. MD simulations can be used to observe the behavior of drug molecules as they interact with the hydrophobic cavity of cyclodextrins in real time and in explicit physiological environments, thereby providing a detailed understanding of the host-guest interactions. These simulations enable the study of binding energetics, including the determination of free energy and potential of mean force (PMF) profiles, which are critical for predicting the stability of complexes and complementing experimental techniques. Furthermore, MD simulations can reveal the complexity of conformational basins visited by both the drug and cyclodextrin during complex formation, an advantage over quantum chemistry-based techniques. By using advanced techniques such as umbrella sampling (Kumar et al., 2024a) or metadynamics, one can overcome the limitations of traditional molecular dynamics and obtain a more comprehensive picture of molecular interactions. They provide a cost-effective and time-efficient method for screening and predicting the behavior of new drug formulations containing cyclodextrins. Moreover, combined MD simulations and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) studies have been successfully used in the past to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the fundamental molecular mechanisms underlying the complexation of CyDs with guest compounds (González-Méndez et al., 2020; Schönbeck, 2018).

Despite the large amount of theoretical data available on cyclodextrins and their complexes, there are surprisingly few studies aimed at understanding the effects of cosolvents on complexation. Gaining atomic-scale insight into these cosolvent phenomena is crucial for predicting and improving the behavior of new drug formulations based on cyclodextrins. For example, Zhang and co-workers (Zhang et al., 2012) used molecular dynamics simulations to study the structural behavior of β-cyclodextrin and its complexes with isoflavonoids in various alcohol solutions. Their study highlighted differences in the flexibility of cyclodextrins depending on the type of cosolvent, its influence on complexation, and the role of water in the presence of different cosolvents. The use of cosolvents reduces the number of strong hydrogen bonds between cyclodextrin and water and between water and water, thereby favoring the entrapment process for nonpolar drugs. In this case,

the cosolvent must be a water-miscible or partially miscible organic solvent (Li et al., 1999). Similarly, Rungrim and co-workers (Rungrim et al., 2015) used a combined experimental and molecular dynamics simulation approach to investigate the effect of ethanol as a cosolvent on the formation of the inclusion complex between α-mangostin and β-cyclodextrin. They showed that higher ethanol concentrations improved the solubility of α-mangostin while maintaining a binary binding mode. In addition, another molecular dynamics simulation study (Boonyarattanakalin et al., 2015) examined the interactions of the anti-HIV drug UC781 with three types of cyclodextrins in aqueous ethanol solutions and showed that ethanol and the type of cyclodextrin influenced the formation of inclusion complexes, with UC781 forming the most stable complexes with 2,6-dimethyl-β-CyD in the presence of ethanol. These results highlight the importance of considering cosolvent effects and understanding them at the atomic level when studying cyclodextrin complexes to improve drug formulation strategies.

The aim of the present study was to investigate the role of cosolvent and molecular mechanisms involved in PCZH—NO₃/cyclodextrin complexation in DMSO-water mixtures. We selected β-CyD for the present study due to its cavity size of 6.0–6.5 Å (Szente et al., 2018), which is optimal for accommodating the triazole moiety and the substituted aromatic rings of propiconazole nitrate. This choice was further supported by our previous studies (Fifere et al., 2012; Minea et al., 2016), which demonstrated that β-CyD forms stable inclusion complexes with propiconazole. Both theoretical studies based on atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and experimental NMR analyses were used for the investigation. DMSO competes with both water and the drug for cavity occupancy, and MD allows us to dissect the dynamics of this competition in atomistic detail. Our results reveal that the inclusion complex formation is significantly influenced by the solvent composition, with a preference for DMSO over water within the CyD cavity. Detailed analysis of root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) and radial distribution functions (RDF) highlighted the hydrophobic and hydrogen-bonding interactions driving this process while the PMF calculations underscored the favorable energetics of complexation in the presence of DMSO. Complementary NMR data provided further confirmation in very good agreement with the theoretical calculations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Molecular dynamics simulations

The β-Cyclodextrin (β-CyD) molecule was described using the GLY-CAM 06 force field (Kirschner et al., 2008), while the General Amber Force Field (GAFF) (Wang et al., 2004) was used for propiconazole nitrate (PCZH—NO₃). Partial atomic charges for PCZH—NO₃ were derived using the Restrained Electrostatic Potential (RESP) methodology (Woods and Chappelle, 2000) at the HF/6-31G* level of theory using the R.E.D. III Tools suite (Dupradeau et al., 2010) and GAMESS-US software (Schmidt et al., 1993). The molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed using the GROMACS software suite (Abraham et al., 2015). All simulations were conducted in the NPT ensemble at a temperature of 293 K and a pressure of 1 atm. The Nosé-Hoover thermostat (Martyna et al., 1992) and the Parrinello-Rahman barostat (Parrinello and Rahman, 1981) were used for temperature and pressure coupling. To construct solvated β-CyD/PCZH—NO₃ complexes, appropriate numbers of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and water molecules were added to attain the desired DMSO/H₂O ratios (0 %, 5 %, 10 %, 20 %, 35 %, 50 % and 100 %). The exact molecular compositions are provided in the Supplementary Information (Table SI-2). To compute the Potential of Mean Force (PMF) profiles describing β-CyD/PCZH—NO₃ complex dissociation under different conditions, the reaction coordinate was defined along the symmetry axis of β-CyD, which is perpendicular to both the primary and secondary rim planes and passes through the molecule's center of mass. PCZH—NO₃ was pulled along this axis, exiting β-CyD via either the primary or secondary rim, depending on the

case. For umbrella sampling (US) calculations, an appropriate number of US windows were defined along the reaction coordinate to ensure sufficient overlap between histograms. In each window, an umbrella potential was applied to the center of mass of PCZH—NO₃ relative to the center of mass of β -CyD, using a force constant of 5000 kJ/mol. All umbrella sampling simulations were run for 30 ns per window, with snapshots recorded every 2 ps. Only the final 25 ns of each simulation were used for analysis. PMF profiles were calculated using the Weighted Histogram Analysis Method (WHAM) (Kumar et al., 1992) as implemented in GROMACS suite. Statistical errors were estimated using bootstrap analysis (Hub et al., 2010).

2.2. NMR measurements

Materials: β -cyclodextrin was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich; protonated propiconazole nitrate (PCZH—NO₃) was prepared by the treatment of propiconazole (PCZ) with a mixture of nitric and acetic acid in a 1:3 molar ratio in chloroform, at room temperature for 18 h. DMSO-d₆ (99.90 % D) and D₂O (98 % D) were purchased from Eurisotop. Double distilled water was used throughout the study. The NMR spectra have been recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at 400.1 MHz for ¹H nuclei. For the NMR analysis a 5 mm multinuclear inverse detection z-gradient probe was used. ¹H-NMR spectra and H,H ROESY spectra were recorded using standard pulse sequences, as delivered by Bruker, with TopSpin 2.1 PL6 spectrometer control and processing software. Both β -CyD/PCZH—NO₃ samples and the reference samples containing pure compounds were dissolved in D₂O containing 5 %, 10 %, 20 %, 35 % and 50 % DMSO-d₆ (v/v). The proton chemical shifts were reported in ppm, relative to the DMSO-d₆ residual peak (1H: 2.512 ppm).

3. Results

3.1. Molecular dynamics simulations

In any complexation reaction, dominant interactions play a crucial role in determining its direction and progression. A cyclodextrin (CyD) has two distinct rims: (i) the primary rim, which primarily facilitates hydrophobic interactions, and (ii) the secondary hydroxy rim, which is involved mainly in hydrophilic interactions. Consequently, the target compound and solvent compete for interactions with CyD to form an inclusion complex, while the presence of a cosolvent further modulates these interactions. The key driving factors are the properties of the target compound and the solvent/cosolvent system. Additionally, CyD properties, including size and conformational dynamics, influence these interactions, with structural changes occurring in response to variations in the solvent/cosolvent ratio.

To assess these changes, the root mean square displacement (RMSD) of free β -cyclodextrin (β -CyD), without the PCNO₃, was calculated in both pure and mixed DMSO/water systems. The results are presented in Fig. SI-1. The RMSD of all atoms in β -CyD shows no significant variation across different DMSO/water ratios: 0.11 ± 0.027 nm in pure water, 0.11 ± 0.022 nm in pure DMSO, 0.12 ± 0.026 nm at 5 % v/v, 0.11 ± 0.023 nm at 10 % v/v, 0.097 ± 0.019 nm at 20 % v/v, 0.11 ± 0.023 nm at 35 % v/v, and 0.10 ± 0.023 nm at 50 % v/v DMSO/water mixtures. Low RMSD across solvent systems suggests that β -CyD retains structural rigidity, a prerequisite for selective complexation. To further investigate local structural modifications induced by the solvent type, the root mean square fluctuation (RMSF) of each atom in the repeating glucose units was calculated. The averaged results over the seven subunits are presented in Fig. 2, with the atom nomenclature of the glucose monomer also provided in the same figure. RMSF calculations were performed only for pure solvents (water or DMSO), representing extreme cases of different solvent environments. The RMSF values for individual β -CyD atoms were lower in DMSO than in water, although following the same pattern in both solvents. No significant differences were observed for most of the CyD atoms, indicating that CyD oligomer fluctuations are not affected by the choice of solvent. However, increased fluctuations were observed in the marginal units, particularly in the hydroxyl groups at positions 2 and 3, with the most pronounced fluctuations occurring at position 6 (Fig. 2) with both water and DMSO solvents. These fluctuations likely result from potential interactions with the solvent/cosolvent, such as the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds. The RMSF recorded values at positions 2, 3, and 6 indicate enhanced local flexibility in these regions, which is consistent with dynamic side-chain mobility often associated with solvent-exposed or conformationally adaptable sites. High RMSF values of hydroxyl moiety at position 6 reflects primary rim flexibility which affects how PCZH—NO₃ accesses the cavity from the narrower rim.

The next step of our analysis involved investigating the differences in affinity between DMSO and water molecules for the β -CyD cavity, as reflected in the residence times of DMSO molecules within the CyD cavity. This analysis determines which molecule, water or DMSO, preferentially interacts with the CyD interior and how their competition for occupancy of the cavity, in the context of the mixed solvent system, influences the drug complexation. Fig. SI-2 shows that individual DMSO molecules dynamically enter and exit the CyD cavity. Quantitative analysis showed that at 5 % v/v DMSO, individual DMSO molecules exhibited an average exchange rate of 0.19 ns^{-1} within the β -cyclodextrin cavity. At 50 % v/v DMSO, this exchange rate increased to 0.27 ns^{-1} , reflecting shorter residence times per molecule due to the higher number of competing DMSO molecules. As illustrated in Figure SI-2, the cavity remains predominantly occupied throughout the simulations, with time intervals devoid of DMSO occupancy consistently corresponding to the

Fig. 2. Root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) of individual atomic positions in β -CyD, calculated in pure solvent environments (water and DMSO).

presence of water molecules. This mutually exclusive occupancy pattern highlights a dynamic competition between DMSO and water, with DMSO exhibiting a clear preferential binding behavior under all solvent conditions tested. Due to the dynamic nature of the system, DMSO molecules tend to remain inside the CyD cavity, continuously replacing each other, while water molecules preferentially interact with the CyD macromolecule externally via hydrogen bonding with free hydroxyl groups. These findings suggest that DMSO exhibits a higher affinity for CyD through complexation. Consequently, a competitive interaction exists between the PCZH—NO₃ drug and DMSO for inclusion within the CyD cavity.

A more comprehensive understanding of the interactions between CyD and the components of the mixed solvent can be obtained by constructing radial distribution functions (RDFs) between CyD and three reference atoms from water and DMSO, respectively. RDF analysis provides an intuitive representation of the preferred interaction modes of CyD with water and DMSO in the absence of the PCZH—NO₃ target compound. Specifically, RDF calculations focused on the oxygen atom of DMSO to probe its hydrogen bonding capability, and on the methyl carbon atoms to represent hydrophobic interactions. This approach allowed us to distinguish how polar and non-polar interactions contribute to DMSO's preferential positioning within the β -CyD cavity (Fig. 3).

The RDF profiles shown in Fig. 3A for the oxygen atom of water relative to the CyD center of mass (COM) exhibit three distinct peaks. The first peak, located around 1.8 Å, corresponds to water molecules residing inside the central CyD cavity, forming a first-order solvation shell along the inner CyD surface at different concentrations. As expected, this peak is highly prominent in the pure water solvent,

reflecting hydrogen bonding interactions between water molecules and the 1,4 glycosidic and glucopyranosyl oxygen atoms. The second peak, observed at approximately 9.4 Å, corresponds to water molecules interacting with the outer surface of CyD, particularly with the hydroxyl groups on both the small and large rims. This interaction is primarily governed by hydrogen bonding. The third peak, a small shoulder at around 12.4 Å, represents the second solvation shell on the outer CyD surface stabilized by water-water hydrogen bonding.

Fig. 3B presents the RDF profiles for the oxygen atom of DMSO (O_{DMSO}) relative to the CyD center of mass (COM) across different DMSO/H₂O ratios (ranging from 5 % to 100 % H₂O). The first peak, observed at 1.7 Å, corresponds to DMSO molecules residing inside the central CyD cavity, preferentially oriented with their oxygen atoms toward the large (secondary) rim of CyD. The methyl groups of DMSO occupy the central cavity, indicating a preference for hydrophobic interactions. In this configuration, the oxygen atom of DMSO can form hydrogen bonds with the hydroxyl groups of the larger CyD rim. The second peak, located at approximately 4 Å, is observed as a flat shoulder in 5 %–50 % DMSO/H₂O v/v mixtures and becomes more pronounced in pure DMSO. This peak corresponds to DMSO molecules positioned at the entrance of the large rim, where they participate in hydrogen bonds with hydroxyl groups at here. The third peak, located around 9 Å, is clearly visible across all mixture ratios and represents DMSO molecules interacting with the outer surface of CyD, where they form hydrogen bonds with the hydroxyl groups of the large rim. Additionally, a fourth peak appears when pure DMSO is used as the solvent. This peak, observed at approximately 12 Å, corresponds to DMSO molecules interacting hydrophobically with the outer surface of β -cyclodextrin via their methyl groups.

In Fig. 3C, the RDF profiles were calculated for the carbon atoms of the methyl groups in DMSO relative to the CyD COM. The first peak, observed at approximately 1.5 Å, corresponds to DMSO molecules residing inside the central cavity, where their methyl groups preferentially interact with the extended hydrophobic regions of the cavity through van der Waals interactions. In addition, dipole-dipole interactions may occur between the polar sulfoxide group of DMSO and CyD hydroxyl groups. This peak correlates with the first peak of the CyD-O_{DMSO} RDF from Fig. 3B. The second peak, visible only in pure DMSO, corresponds to DMSO molecules positioned at the entrance of the large rim and is related to the second peak of the CyD-O_{DMSO} RDF from Fig. 3B. The third peak corresponds to the fourth peak of the CyD-O_{DMSO} RDF and represents DMSO molecules interacting with the outer CyD surface via their methyl groups.

Theoretical data presented in Fig. SI-2 and Fig. 4 indicate that even at low DMSO concentrations, water molecules within the CyD cavity are displaced by DMSO molecules. The strong affinity of DMSO for the CyD cavity leads to a competitive interaction with PCZH—NO₃ drug for inclusion. This competition is evident from the marked flattening of the first peak in the CyD-O_w RDF across all DMSO/H₂O mixtures (Fig. 3A). At low DMSO concentrations, this peak remains visible, suggesting that the CyD central cavity is still transiently occupied by water molecules.

In the next step, we quantitatively investigated the binding affinity of the complexation process by calculating the potential of mean force (PMF) profiles for different insertion modes of PCZH—NO₃ (the guest) into the CyD host under varying solvent/cosolvent mixture ratios. This analysis aimed to determine the preferred mode of complexation. Fig. SI-3 illustrates the PMF profiles of PCZH—NO₃ complexation with CyD in pure solvents, excluding mixed solvent systems. Based on these profiles, the free energy of complexation was calculated in each case. The findings indicate that for large rim complexation, the binding affinity in DMSO follows the order: dichlorophenyl > alkyl > triazole hetero-aromatic unit, while in water, the order is alkyl > dichlorophenyl > triazole ring. However, the difference between the free energy of binding between dichlorophenyl and alkyl modes of complexation is minor (ΔG around 1 kcal). Visual analysis of the umbrella sampling trajectories provides mechanistic insights into how the complexation process

Fig. 3. Radial distribution functions (RDFs) representing the interactions between CyD and solvent molecules (pure and mixed systems): (A) oxygen atom of water relative to the CyD center of mass, (B) oxygen atom (from the sulfoxide group) of DMSO relative to the CyD center of mass, and (C) carbon atoms (from the methyl groups) of DMSO relative to the CyD center of mass.

Fig. 4. A. PMF interaction profiles in different mixture DMSO/water ratio (from 5 to 50 %) of PCZH—NO₃ with CyD; B. Complexation free energy profile relative to the DMSO/water ratio.

progresses for different binding modes in distinct solvent environments, comparing DMSO and water. In DMSO, the dichlorophenyl binding mode is initiated by the formation of hydrogen bonds between the chlorine atoms of the dichlorophenyl fragment and the hydroxyl (OH) groups of CyD. This initial interaction is followed by full complexation, primarily driven by van der Waals and dipole-dipole interactions, which persist within the CyD cavity. In contrast, in a watery environment, the most favorable binding mode involves the alkyl moiety being enclosed within the CyD cavity. Unlike the dichlorophenyl mode in DMSO, no hydrogen bonds are formed in the initial step of this interaction. However, the equilibrium structure of the complex is stabilized through hydrophobic interactions and additional hydrogen bonds. These hydrogen bonds form between the OH groups at positions 2 and 3 of CyD and the oxygen atoms of the dioxolane non-aromatic heterocycle.

For small rim complexation, the binding affinity in DMSO is ranked as alkyl > dichlorophenyl > triazole, whereas in water it is ranked as dichlorophenyl = alkyl > triazole. The complexation process through the small rim in DMSO follows a trend similar to that observed for large rim complexation in water. Likewise, a comparable trend was observed in water, where the binding affinity of PCZH—NO₃ on the small rim resembles that found for the large rim in DMSO. This suggests that the equilibrium complexation of PCZH—NO₃ in different binding modes is driven by analogous interactions to those governing larger rim complexation. For smaller rim complexation, the hydroxyl groups involved in hydrogen bonding primarily include the ones in position 6. Overall, the PMF profiles in Fig. SI-3 indicate that complexation of the PCZH—NO₃ guest with CyD is thermodynamically favorable for both secondary and primary rim interactions, with a higher affinity for the secondary rim.

To quantitatively evaluate the influence of the DMSO/H₂O ratio (v/v) on binding affinity, we constructed PMF profiles for the complexation process across different solvent ratios, ranging from 5 % to 50 % DMSO/H₂O (v/v). The results are presented in Fig. 4A. For this analysis, we chose only a single complexation geometry, selecting the most favorable binding mode through the large rim in DMSO, where the dichlorophenyl unit is included within the central cavity (Fig. SI-3). According to the PMF profiles presented in Fig. 4A, the interaction between PCZH—NO₃ and CyD is most favorable at 5 % DMSO/H₂O (v/v), with a ΔG value of -6.1 kcal/mol, and least favorable at 50 % DMSO/H₂O (v/v) with a ΔG value of -2.85 kcal/mol. The results indicate that DMSO as a cosolvent plays a significant role in the complexation process, gradually reducing the free energy of binding as the DMSO/H₂O (v/v) ratio increases. Based on the PMF calculation results presented in Fig. SI-3 and Fig. 4A, we constructed a comprehensive free energy profile for the complexation process as a function of the DMSO/water ratio, shown in Fig. 4B. The theoretical calculations indicate that the presence of DMSO

as a cosolvent still supports the complexation of PCZH—NO₃ with CyD, with only minor effects at low concentrations up to 10 % DMSO/H₂O (v/v). However, at concentrations exceeding 50 % DMSO/H₂O (v/v), complex formation is likely inhibited, as DMSO at these concentrations reduces the free energy of complexation to approximately -3 kcal/mol, a value comparable to the thermal energy at room temperature (~0.6 kcal/mol).

3.2. NMR experiments

The ¹H-NMR spectra of β-CyD (Fig. SI-4A), PCZH—NO₃ (Fig. SI-4B) and β-CyD/PCZH—NO₃ (Fig. SI-4C) inclusion complex, recorded in 95 % D₂O and 5 % DMSO-d₆ are presented in supporting information. The complex formation in the studied solvents was monitored through variations in the chemical shifts of specific protons in both the host and guest molecules. When the inclusion complex is formed, the cyclodextrin inner protons (H-3' and H-5') suffer an up-field shift due to the magnetic anisotropy effects produced by the guest molecule. In this case, the formation of the inclusion complexes was also confirmed by the chemical shift changes of PCZH—NO₃ aromatic protons. The ¹H-NMR spectrum of free (native) propiconazole (Fig. SI-4B) shows signals corresponding to two diastereoisomers, consistent with previous reports (Fifere et al., 2012; Vialaton et al., 2001) in a ratio of 1:2, as determined from the integral values.

Changes in resonance frequencies are observed for H-3' and H-5' β-CyD inner protons and for the aromatic protons from both triazole (H-3 and H-5) and 2,4-dichlorophenyl (H-17, H-19 and H-20) rings of PCZH—NO₃, depending on the used solvent combination. The chemical shift variation of the aliphatic protons from PCZH—NO₃, could not be followed because of the complex signals multiplicities given by the scalar couplings. The chemical shifts values of individual compounds and inclusion complexes, as well as the chemical shifts differences, are summarized in Table SI-1. As it can be seen, the chemical shifts differences are dependent on the added DMSO percent. The chemical shift perturbation curves across DMSO percent for H-3 and H-5 protons from beta-cyclodextrin are represented in Figure SI-5. The upfield shift of the H-3' β-CyD inner proton is more prominent (-0.036 ppm) in the 95 % D₂O - 5 % DMSO solvent mixture and becomes less significant as the DMSO percent increases being only -0.003 ppm in the 50 % D₂O - 50 % DMSO solvent mixture. For H-5' β-CyD inner proton the upfield shift is greater than for H-3', being -0.089 ppm in the 95 % D₂O - 5 % DMSO solvent mixture and -0.012 ppm in the 50 % D₂O - 50 % DMSO solvent mixture. The decreasing trend of chemical shifts differences with the DMSO increasing concentration can suggest a weakening of the interactions between β-CyD and PCZH—NO₃, caused by the DMSO presence. Most probably, when DMSO percent is above 50 %, the complex

will not be formed.

Besides changes in resonance frequencies, the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of $\beta\text{-CyD/PCZH-NO}_3$ inclusion complexes present splittings for several signals as presented in Fig. SI-4C and Fig. 5. This phenomenon is observed very well for the aromatic signals and can be attributed to the chiral chemical shift reagent property of cyclodextrins. After a close inspection of the chemical structure of propiconazole nitrate, it can be deduced that it may form four diastereoisomeric complexes with $\beta\text{-CyD}$. The presence of these four diastereoisomers is clearly demonstrated by the appearance of four peaks in the interval 8.5–8.8 ppm (corresponding to H-5 protons of PCZH-NO₃). The chemical shifts differences of the PCZH-NO₃ aromatic protons, for all the isomeric forms, are also directly dependent of the DMSO percent, becoming less significant as the DMSO concentration increases (see Table SI-1 for values).

For example, in the case of PCZH-NO₃ proton H-5, that was more straightforward to follow due to its singlet shape, significant upfield shifts of -0.112 ppm and -0.133 ppm were obtained for the two major stereoisomers, in the 95 % D₂O - 5 % DMSO solvent mixture. In the 50 % D₂O - 50 % DMSO solvent mixture, the signals for these two major stereoisomers overlap, being upfield shifted with only -0.038 ppm. As for the two minor isomers, upfield shifts of -0.06 ppm were obtained in the 95 % D₂O - 5 % DMSO and -0.03 ppm in 50 % D₂O - 50 % DMSO solvent mixture. The rest of the aromatic protons (H-3, H-17, H-15 and H-20) were also followed with mainly downfield shifts obtained for the different D₂O - DMSO solvents ratio included in this study (Table SI-1).

Similarly with the case of other nitrogen containing heterocyclic salts we further confirmed the formation of inclusion complexes from ROESY (rotating frame Overhauser effect spectroscopy) experiments. In this type of experiment both inter- and intra-molecular interactions can be observed.

The ROESY spectra of $\beta\text{-CyD/PCZH-NO}_3$ inclusion complexes showed intra-molecular NOE cross-peaks between H-3', H-5' $\beta\text{-CyD}$ inner protons and H-17, H-19 and H-20 PCZH-NO₃ protons, clearly visible in the 95 % D₂O - 5 % DMSO (Fig. 6A) and in the 80 % D₂O - 20 % DMSO

(Fig. 6B) solvent mixtures. These PCZH-NO₃ protons belong to 2,4-dichlorophenyl ring, thus it might be concluded that this ring enters inside the $\beta\text{-CyD}$ cavity. It is worth mentioning that even if the interaction between $\beta\text{-CyD}$ and PCZH-NO₃ decreases with DMSO concentration, in the 50 % D₂O - 50 % DMSO solvent mixture this interaction is still sufficient to allow chiral discrimination since splitting of the H-3, H-5, H-20 signals and widening of the H-19 signal are observed for the PCZH-NO₃ minor isomer. This is also visible in ROESY spectrum by the appearance of weak intra-molecular NOE cross-peaks between H-3', H-5' $\beta\text{-CyD}$ inner protons and H-17, H-19 and H-20 PCZH-NO₃ protons (Fig. 6C).

4. Discussions

This study combines experimental and computational approaches to investigate how the DMSO/water ratio affects the dynamics and thermodynamics of inclusion complexation. Few studies have examined co-solvent effects in drug-cyclodextrin complexation, and to our knowledge, this is the first to show a concentration-dependent destabilization mechanism involving competition between DMSO and a drug for the $\beta\text{-CyD}$ cavity.

The molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) experiments provided complementary insights into the formation and stability of the inclusion complex between $\beta\text{-cyclodextrin}$ (CyD) and propiconazole nitrate (PCZH-NO₃) in mixed DMSO/H₂O solvent systems. The interplay between solvent composition, complexation dynamics, and molecular interactions is critical in understanding how the inclusion process is influenced by competitive interactions with the solvent molecules.

The MD simulations revealed that CyD/PCZH-NO₃ remains structurally stable across all studied solvent mixtures. This finding aligns with the NMR experimental results, which demonstrate systematic chemical shift changes in $\beta\text{-CyD}$'s inner protons (H-3' and H-5') upon complex formation. These upfield shifts, indicative of the inclusion of PCZH-NO₃

Fig. 5. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of $\beta\text{-CyD/PCZH-NO}_3$ inclusion complexes showing the chemical shifts variations and splitting patterns as a function of DMSO percent.

Fig. 6. Expansions of ROESY spectra of β -CyD/PCZH-NO₃ inclusion complex recorded in (A) 95 % D₂O and 5 % DMSO, (B) 80 % D₂O and 20 % DMSO and (C) 50 % D₂O and 50 % DMSO.

inside the β -CyD cavity, become less evident as the DMSO concentration increases, suggesting a progressive weakening of host-guest interactions in the presence of higher cosolvent levels, which aligns very well with the PMF simulation data.

One of the key observations from both MD simulations and NMR spectra is the competitive binding of DMSO and PCZH-NO₃ within the β -CyD cavity. The MD results show that DMSO molecules exhibit a strong affinity for the β -CyD cavity, effectively displacing water molecules even at low concentrations. The calculated radial distribution functions (RDFs) illustrate that DMSO preferentially positions its methyl groups within the cavity while its sulfoxide oxygen interacts with the hydroxyl groups of β -CyD, forming stabilizing hydrogen bonds. These findings are corroborated by NMR data, which reveal a systematic decrease in the chemical shift variations of both β -CyD and PCZH-NO₃ protons as the DMSO concentration increases. The reduced magnitude of chemical shifts at higher DMSO percentages reflects a diminished host-guest interaction, reinforcing the computational observation that DMSO effectively competes with PCZH-NO₃ for β -CyD inclusion.

Thermodynamic analysis of the complexation process, obtained from PMF calculations in the MD study, further supports the cosolvent-dependent nature of the interaction. The free energy of binding decreases progressively with increasing DMSO concentration, with the most favorable binding occurring in 5 % DMSO ($\Delta G \approx -6$ kcal/mol), while at 50 % DMSO, the binding affinity is significantly reduced ($\Delta G \approx$

-2 kcal/mol). These computational predictions align with the NMR data, which indicate that beyond 50 % DMSO, the chemical shift differences become negligible, implying that the complex formation is significantly weakened. The ROESY NMR spectra further confirm that while the β -CyD/PCZH-NO₃ interaction persists at 50 % DMSO, the intensity of NOE cross-peaks between β -CyD inner protons (H-3', H-5') and PCZH-NO₃ protons (H-17, H-19, and H-20) is markedly reduced, indicating a less stable complex.

The spatial orientation of PCZH-NO₃ inside the β -CyD cavity is another point of convergence between MD simulations and NMR findings. MD simulations suggest that the 2,4-dichlorophenyl moiety of PCZH-NO₃ preferentially enters the β -CyD cavity, stabilized by van der Waals and dipole-dipole interactions, particularly in aqueous environments. However, in DMSO, the difference in preference compared to the alkyl group entering the cavity is minor. ROESY NMR spectra confirm this preferential orientation through the detection of NOE interactions between the aromatic protons of the 2,4-dichlorophenyl ring and the inner protons of β -CyD, reinforcing the computational prediction. Even though DMSO reduces the binding affinity, the spatial arrangement of the guest molecule inside the cavity remains discernible, further validating the MD-derived interaction model.

Taken together, these findings present a coherent picture of the solvent-driven modulation of the β -CyD/PCZH-NO₃ inclusion complex. The combination of computational and experimental approaches

provides robust evidence that DMSO disrupts complex formation by competing with PCZH—NO₃ for inclusion within the β-CyD cavity. However, our MD simulation data provides a quantitative perspective on the DMSO/H₂O ratios at which the complexation process remains robust. While complexation is favored at low DMSO concentrations, increasing the cosolvent level progressively weakens the interaction, ultimately reaching a point where the complex is no longer thermodynamically favorable. A DMSO concentration of ~5 % to ~10 % (v/v) seems optimal to enhance solubility of hydrophobic compounds while minimizing biological interference. DMSO is commonly used for this purpose, enabling consistent dose–response analysis without impacting microbial toxicity in short-term assays (Modrzyński et al., 2019). Studies on lipid membranes have shown that up to 10 % DMSO does not significantly alter the structural properties of DMPC or DPPC liposomes (Amaral et al., 2024). While cytotoxicity has been reported at lower concentrations under specific conditions, such as interference with sulfur metabolism (Kaczor-Kamińska et al., 2024) or membrane damage in blood and endothelial cells at 0.6 % (Yi et al., 2017), these effects typically arise in long-term or systemic exposure scenarios. These results have important implications for understanding host-guest interactions in mixed solvent systems and offer valuable insights into the design and optimization of cyclodextrin-based drug delivery systems.

5. Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive investigation of the formation of inclusion complexes between cyclodextrins (CyDs) and PCZH—NO₃, a triazole derivative with antifungal actions in different solvent environments, combining molecular dynamics simulations with NMR spectroscopy. The results highlight the critical role of solvent composition and show that DMSO exhibits a pronounced preference for interacting with the CyD cavity compared to water, even at a low DMSO:water ratio. Root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) and radial distribution functions (RDF) analysis revealed that hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonds are the determining factors for the stabilization of these complexes. Furthermore, potential of the mean force (PMF) calculations confirmed the favorable energetics of complexation, especially in mixtures with low DMSO concentration, where binding affinities were strongest. ¹H-NMR and ROESY spectra offered experimental validation, revealing chemical shift variations and chiral discrimination within the inclusion complexes. These experimental observations were in good agreement with theoretical predictions, further supporting the dynamic interplay between solvents in driving complexation. The study sheds light on the competition between DMSO and water for CyD inclusion of PCZH—NO₃, giving atomic scale information on the mechanism that governs the host-guest dynamics. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the CyD inclusion complexes formation in solvent mixtures, with implications for their application in drug delivery systems. The results underscore the importance of tailoring solvent environments to optimize CyD-based formulations for specific guest molecules.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve language, grammar and readability of the text. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dragos L. Isac: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Petru Tîrnovan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Alina Nicolescu:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Adrian Fifere:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Andrei Neamtu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization, Formal analysis. **Mariana Pinteala:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.ejps.2025.107248.

Data availability

The datasets and computer scripts used in this study are available upon request to the corresponding author.

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